

MODERN METHODS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING TO STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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Abstract. The article describes modern methods of teaching English to students with disabilities. The possibilities of inclusive teaching of a foreign language are considered using the example of visually impaired and blind students as part of a study group of students who do not have visual impairments.

Key words: teaching English, students with disabilities, inclusive education, modern methods, teacher's experience.

The last decade has been characterized by the growing attention of the teaching community to conducting research to determine the possibilities of implementing inclusive education for individuals with disabilities at all levels of education. The fundamental principle of inclusive education is the exclusion of any discrimination against schoolchildren and students and, at the same time, the creation of special conditions for students with special educational needs. Supporters of inclusive education believe that everyone has the right to receive a full education.

In recent years, Uzbek society has largely turned to face people with disabilities, has become much more tolerant and accepting of them, but sympathetic attitude alone is not enough, specific actions are needed, and in education, scientifically based actions. An attentive and sensitive attitude of a teacher to students with visual impairments is certainly an important condition for the success of the educational process. Such an attitude liberates the student, allows him to better reveal his personal potential. However, we should not forget that a student with disabilities is in the same classroom with ordinary students and is involved in the traditional educational process, which makes its own demands on students. The teacher must plan each lesson and academic semester, as well as the practical implementation of the objectives of the university curriculum as a whole. The teacher must pay attention to each student during classroom work [1].

In connection with the organization of inclusive education, teachers have defined and completed the following tasks when working with students with disabilities in teaching a foreign language based on modern methods:

Students mastered the above discipline during the first and second years. Based on modern methods, students with disabilities take part in classroom classes together with other students in their study group. In these classes, students with disabilities use specialized technical means of receiving and transmitting information in a form accessible to them, as well as electronic educational resources.

For example, students with visual disabilities use the most common method of reading and writing - Braille, invented by the Frenchman Louis Braille. This is a tactile reading system for the blind, consisting of six-dot signs called cells or squares. Braille exists in different languages and is used by the blind all over the world. Due to the limited speed of writing in Braille, currently the classroom mainly uses a computer, as well as specialized technologies created on the basis of the Braille font. Computer typhlotecnologies are the general name for a set of tools that provide blind and visually impaired people with the ability to independently use a personal computer and programs for technical devices [2]. The ability of people with visual disabilities to independently use computer typhlotecnologies is one of the important areas in the process of inclusive professionally oriented training of students. The

following professionally oriented training devices are installed on the computer of visually impaired students:

There are also specialized speech synthesizers (additional voices that allow working with foreign languages) for the NVDA program. They are installed separately. During the lesson, the speech access technical device reproduces everything that is written on the computer screen. If special synthesizers are available, this technical device recognizes the language in which the text is written and pronounces it in compliance with the rules for reading this language (Russian, English, German, etc.). Visually impaired students perceive information by ear through an earphone, which allows them to read books, work with textbooks, and use the Internet [3]. Thus, teaching a foreign language to students with disabilities based on computer technology and the Internet is an intersection of various fields of knowledge, and is closely related to the progress of information technology, software development, research in the field of artificial intelligence, as well as the theory and practice of computer-based learning.

Today, the possibilities of computer technology include a variety of educational programs for students with disabilities, among which are teaching individual aspects of a foreign language, developing speech skills, control programs for assessing language knowledge and programs introducing the socio-cultural aspects of the country where the language is studied. To organize such activities, certain technical characteristics are necessary, especially high-speed Internet access during classes for effective data exchange, especially by students with disabilities. However, the use of information from the Internet as a form of independent work in free time should be widely used in everyday teaching practice.

To summarize, we can conclude that the development of Internet technologies and artificial intelligence has opened up limitless opportunities for enriching the

process of learning a foreign language, making it more interesting for modern students with disabilities, as well as more effective due to new, accessible means. The development of Internet technologies allows using modern methods for teaching foreign languages, students with disabilities can use special applications, online platforms and artificial intelligence capabilities to gain new knowledge. Each modern method has its own characteristics, and the scope of its application depends on this.

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